

ARTICLE

Cost-sensitive Tree SHAP for Explaining Cost-sensitive Tree-based Models

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Abstract

Cost-sensitive ensemble learning is a combination of two approaches, ensemble learning and cost-sensitive learning. In this work, the focus is on tree-based ensemble models in a cost-sensitive framework. Particularly, cost-sensitive random forest model, where base models are generated using the same cost-sensitive decision tree (CSDT) learning algorithm. The CSDT is a variant of the decision tree algorithm incorporating misclassification costs into the learning process. All tree-based models characterize nice graphical representation that can explain a model's decision-making process. However, the depth of the tree and the number of base models in the ensemble can be a limiting factor in comprehending the model's decision for each sample. The increasingly popular Tree SHAP method, a variation of the SHAP methodology for tree-based models, can facilitate the explanation of deep tree-based models. However, the current implementation of the Tree SHAP method is limited only to several tree-based models, excluding the cost-sensitive tree-based classifiers. Our previous work introduced a cost-sensitive tree explanation method based on the Tree SHAP method. Here, we extend the introduced methodology to cost-sensitive ensemble models. Using the proposed cost-sensitive tree explainer we analyse the stability of explanations for single and ensemble cost-sensitive tree models.

KEY WORDS

Explainable Artificial Intelligence, Tree SHAP, Cost-sensitive learning, Ensemble learning, Tree-based models

1 | INTRODUCTION

In classification problems the cost of making an error and wrongly classifying a sample can differ from sample to sample, that is, the samples can have different misclassification costs. Cost-sensitive learning is a subgroup of machine learning classification algorithms that can counteract problems where samples do not have the same misclassification costs. The misclassification costs enable specifying the relative importance of different kinds of prediction errors. In the binary classification framework, the cost of misclassifying a sample is a function of the actual and predicted class, represented as a two-dimensional cost matrix, where rows of the matrix are actual classes and columns are predicted classes. The cost of a certain type of error may be a constant or conditional on each sample in the dataset. Therefore, two types of cost matrices can be distinguished, class-dependent and example-dependent cost matrices. In other words, either there is an assumption that all samples from the same class have the same cost of misclassification or each sample has its cost matrix defined.

A former, much stronger assumption can be used in the context of imbalanced classification. Namely, class imbalance in a two-class classification framework can be described as a problem where one class is underrepresented. When dealing with class imbalance, the wrong classification of samples from a class with a smaller number of samples (minority class) is much more undesired compared to the wrong classification of majority class samples (the class with a larger number of samples). Accordingly, it can be assumed that minority samples have a higher cost of misclassification and cost-sensitive learning algorithms can be used for tackling the class imbalance problem. This is important due to the vast amount of data with intrinsically imbalanced distribution in many domains including fraud detection, credit rating, medicine and others. In many

Abbreviations: CSDT, cost-sensitive decision tree; CSRF, cost-sensitive random forest; SHAP, Shapley Additive Explanation Method.

domains, the cost matrix can be determined based on domain knowledge. However, in cases when determining the cost matrix is not possible, it can be assumed that the matrix is class-dependent and costs can be estimated during the cross-validation procedure. The assumption about the example-dependent cost matrix is rarely used in practice as it is typically unknown. However, in our research, we used datasets for which example-dependent cost matrices are available. More importantly, the costs are known for all samples, which is the main reason for choosing those particular datasets. When costs are example-dependent and are known for only some samples, machine learning models are used for the estimation of the unknown costs [29]. The cost matrix is properly defined when conditions defined in [11] are satisfied, which implies that no column in the matrix dominates the other.

In general, ensemble learning is a widely used supervised learning approach for classification problems where weak base learners are combined to create much stronger ones. In our previous article [15] we primarily dealt with uncovering the decision-making process of cost-sensitive decision trees (CSDT). A natural extension of cost-sensitive models are cost-sensitive ensemble models, with cost-sensitive models as base learners. In this paper our focus is on the cost-sensitive random forest model (CSRF) introduced in [2].

In this algorithm, base models are generated using the CSDT learning algorithm. After each base CSDT model has been generated, the final prediction from the cost-sensitive ensemble model is determined as in the cost-insensitive [‡] ensemble models. That is, the prediction of the ensemble is the class predicted by the majority of base learners, where if the result is tied, the final class is chosen arbitrarily. However, for real-life production applications providing a model with good performance metrics is not enough. Stakeholders expect models not only to be accurate but also reliable, transparent, and explainable.

In general, the tree-based classifiers have a nice graphical representation of the model, which facilitates understanding of the decision-making process. However, the depth of the tree and the number of base models in an ensemble can be a limiting factor in comprehending the (ensemble's) model's decision for each sample. An additional obstacle for the CSDT and cost-sensitive ensemble models based on CSDT is the implementation of the methods. Fortunately, for tree-based models there is Tree SHAP, a model-specific explainable artificial intelligence (xAI) method for the exact calculation of SHAP values [21, 13, 24]. However, the current implementation of the Tree SHAP method is limited to only several tree-based models, excluding the cost-sensitive tree-based classifiers. The objective of our research is to extend the previously introduced cost-sensitive version of Tree SHAP for CSDT, which also should facilitate the explanation of ensemble cost-sensitive tree-based models.

The Tree SHAP does not treat a machine learning model as a black box, rather it uses its tree-based structure to compute SHAP values exactly. Considering that cost-sensitive tree models have a cost matrix as an additional input parameter which is used in the tree-building process and later in terminal nodes for the decision-making process, the cost matrix had to be incorporated into the Tree SHAP algorithm. Firstly, the CSDT algorithm is modified in a way that instead of using class labels in the nodes of the cost-sensitive tree as defined in [7], the cost-sensitive tree model uses the probabilities that are cost-dependent. Additionally, more technical changes are made to the attributes of the existing tree object, which is given as a dictionary object, and used as a representation of the trained cost-sensitive tree model. Thereafter, an adaptation of the Tree SHAP algorithm to handle the cost-sensitive tree-based models was created. A more detailed description of the methodology is presented in the second part of the third section.

The rest of this article is organized as follows. In the next section, we give an overall description of the cost-sensitive learning methods and xAI methods for tree-based models. In the first subsection of Section 3, we describe the CSDT method including extension on cost-sensitive ensemble methods, followed by an explanation of the proposed cost-sensitive Tree SHAP method. Next, we present the experimental setup with a description of the datasets used. Finally, we report the results with concluding remarks and directions for future work.

2 | RELATED WORK

One of the first articles on the cost-sensitive classification problem dates back to 1994 [10], and since then numerous other methods have been proposed as a solution to the problem in the literature. The methods can be classified into three main classes.

The first class of methods deals with modifying the inputs (or a pre-processing step) to a given classifier. This can be achieved by re-weighting the training set either by over-sampling [11] or under-sampling [30] in a cost-proportionate manner and then training the given model in the usual manner. This class of methods does not modify the architecture of the classifier or the underlying training algorithm in any way. The second class of methods deals with modifying the probability outputs of a given classifier (usually a tree-based model). This is done by trying to quantify different tradeoffs between various decisions

[‡] Cost-insensitive model is said to be a model that considers costs of both types of errors as equal.

using probabilities and the cost that accompanies such decisions [4], [5]. The final class of methods tries to make the classifier and the underlying training method cost-sensitive. In the literature, this has been done for decision trees by introducing the misclassification cost into the construction of the tree. This can be achieved by modifying the impurity measures with respect to cost and by introducing cost-sensitive pruning mechanisms [10], [16], [17], [18], [27].

The previously listed articles dealt with the class-dependent cost-sensitive case. The article by Correa, B. A. et al. [7] introduced the methodology for the example-dependant cost-sensitive classification problem and it is considered a state-of-the-art example-dependant cost-sensitive decision tree method (the implementation can be found in the costcla repository [1]). The same author also builds on top of its decision tree method to introduce the cost-sensitive ensemble models, namely the cost-sensitive bagging classifier and the cost-sensitive random forest classifier [2]. The article also introduces a metric that can be used to define a given problem as cost-insensitive, class-dependent cost-sensitive, or example-dependent cost-sensitive.

It should be noted that none of the articles mentioned in this section dealt with the explanation of the proposed cost-sensitive models. Also, in the literature, there is a limited amount of articles dealing solely with the interpretable machine learning models for imbalanced data, of which the cost-sensitive classification is a special case [9], [12]. On the other hand, the well-known Tree SHAP [21] algorithm is a great tool for understanding tree-based models, but the current implementation is not compatible with the costcla library.

To the best of the present author's knowledge, the previous article by the present authors [15] is the first article dealing with the explanation methods for cost-sensitive decision trees.

3 | METHODOLOGY

The first part of this section is devoted to the concept of cost-sensitive learning with a focus on tree-based models. The concept is further extended to ensemble learning with the cost-sensitive tree-based model architecture. Afterward, we introduced the Tree SHAP method from the xAI framework which facilitates the explanation of tree-based machine learning models, followed by modification of the Tree SHAP method that has been required to adapt it for tree-based models that are cost-sensitive.

3.1 | Cost-sensitive decision tree model

In general, the cost-sensitive models are machine learning models able to handle samples with different misclassification costs. A subclass of cost-sensitive machine learning models are tree-based cost-sensitive models. The tree-building procedure is binary and recursive, similar to the procedure in classical (cost-insensitive) decision tree algorithms. As in any tree-building procedure, the top-down greedy search is used as it is computationally impossible to consider every possible partition of the feature space. However, the CSDT uses a cost-sensitive splitting measure that depends on the cost matrix. At each splitting step, the cost-sensitive gain measure, named savings score in [7], is calculated. The saving score is expressed as expected misclassification cost reduction. Following the notation used for defining classical decision tree algorithm as in [26], the cost-sensitive gain measure is defined as:

$$Gain(j) = \frac{Q_p - (Q_l + Q_r)}{Q_p} \quad (1)$$

where the Q_p is the cost-based impurity measure of a parent node whilst Q_l and Q_r represent the cost-based impurity measures of the left and right child nodes, respectively. The cost-based impurity measure is the minimal cost of labeling a given node to a particular class. Mathematically written:

$$Q_m = \min\{cost(f_0(m)), cost(f_1(m))\} \quad (2)$$

where $f_k(m)$, $k \in \{0, 1\}$, is defined as is function that assigns class label k to all samples that belong to the node m and $cost(f_k(m))$ is defined as misclassification cost at node m if costs for correct classification are zero. If the costs for correct classification are not equal to zero, the $cost(f_k(m))$ is calculated as:

$$cost(f_k(m)) = \sum_{x_i \in m} I(y_i \neq k)C(y_i \neq k, k) + I(y_i = k)C(y_i = k, k) \quad (3)$$

where the \mathbf{C} represents a cost matrix, either class-dependent or sample-dependent. Since the cost-sensitive gain measure is defined using a cost-based impurity measure, the higher the cost-sensitive gain measure for a feature, the higher the reduction of the cost of misclassification.

Each terminal node in the CSDT model is allocated to the least costly class. This means that the terminal nodes are labeled to the class which minimizes the misclassification cost. Given a cost matrix with zero cost for correct classification, the CSDT method introduced in [7], classifies a sample in the node m to the least costly class $k(m)$:

$$k(m) = \underset{k}{\operatorname{argmin}} \operatorname{cost}(f_k(m)) \quad (4)$$

meaning that if the minority class is denoted as positive and the majority class as negative, the cost of predicting a negative/positive label in the node is equal to the misclassification costs for positive/negative samples in the node wrongly classified as negative/positive. This labeling scheme, known as hard-labeling, is proposed in the CSDT method introduced by Correa, B. A. et al. [7]. The hard-labeling of terminal nodes means that a label assigned to each node is binary denoting the class membership of all the samples in each node. On the other hand, in the soft-labeling approach, a label assigned to each node is probability. That is, a terminal node is labeled as a probability vector with a size corresponding to the number of classes. The class label is then determined based on the highest probability score. The reason for introducing soft-labeling in the CSDT is two-fold: firstly, having probability membership for each sample gives us information on how confident the model is in the prediction that the given sample belongs to the minority (more costly) class. The second reason is seen in the definition of the SHAP methodology we seek to apply to the CSDT and ensemble models based on the CSDT, where the SHAP values of all the input features sum up to the difference between expected model output, which is the prior probability of a class and the probability-based output of the model for the sample being explained.

In order not to lose the fact that labeling nodes in a cost-sensitive tree model should be cost-dependent, the soft-labeling is introduced by defining cost-sensitive probability as follows:

$$p_{mk} = \frac{\operatorname{cost}(f_{\bar{k}}(m))}{\operatorname{cost}(f_{\bar{k}}(m)) + \operatorname{cost}(f_k(m))} \quad (5)$$

where $\operatorname{cost}(f_k(m), k \in \{0, 1\})$ is the cost of labeling node m as k , and $\operatorname{cost}(f_{\bar{k}}(m))$ is the cost of labeling node to the class other than k . The cost-sensitive probability for labeling the node m as the positive/negative is the (misclassification) cost of labeling all samples in the node as negative/positive divided by the total cost[§]. Notice, if there is an equal number of samples from both classes in the node and costs for correct classification are zero, then due to the higher cost of misclassification for positive (minority) samples, there is a higher probability of labeling the node as positive. Furthermore, even in a situation where there is a smaller number of minority samples in the node, it can still be labeled as positive if the cost of making an error on the minority class is high enough. Therefore, the CSDT model has a built-in bias towards the minority class, directed by misclassification costs.

As for the cost-insensitive decision tree, the CSDT algorithm grows the tree until a stopping criterion is met. Standard pruning methods are not suitable for cost-sensitive methods as they are based on error-rate minimization or accuracy maximization. In the CSDT, modified cost-complexity pruning includes costs of misclassification. The cost-sensitive pruning method generates a series of sub-trees and then examines the cost reduction of each of them, taking into account both the costs and the complexity (size) of the tree. The process successively collapses the internal nodes which produce the highest relative cost reduction weighted by the relative decrease of the tree size (measured as the number of internal nodes). Using this pruning method, nodes of the tree that do not contribute to the minimization of the misclassification cost will be pruned, regardless of their impact on the accuracy of the model.

3.2 | Cost-sensitive random forest model

Many research utilize cost-sensitivity under multiple classifier systems. A natural extension of cost-sensitive decision tree methods are cost-sensitive ensemble methods with cost-sensitive decision trees as base learners. The general idea of the Cost-sensitive Random Forest (CSRf) is to induce different CSDT classifiers by using different bootstrap subsets from the training data like in the classical random forest method. The classifiers are generated to maximum size with the following modification contrasting to the random forest method: instead of selecting a subset of attributes for the optimal split at each node, the algorithm only searches through a fixed subset of randomly selected attributes, as in random subspace method [28]. The random subspace algorithm like random forest requires less computational cost since the method uses random subsets of features and give more stable results compared to random forest. The difference compared to classical random forest method is that the feature subset

[§] The total cost is the cost of misclassifying all samples.

is selected for entire decision tree rather than at each split point in the tree. After a desired number of the CSDT classifiers is generated, their predictions are aggregated to make the final prediction of the CSRf classifier. In the hard-voting scenario, the final prediction from ensemble model is a class predicted from larger number of base learners, where if the result is tied, the final class is chosen arbitrarily.

If we consider an ensemble of B cost-sensitive decision trees each induced on a random subset S_j of the training set S by applying the CSDT learning algorithm, where each CSDT classifier for simplicity will be denoted as $h_i(S_j) \equiv h_i$, $i = 1, \dots, B$, then the h_i outputs the class prediction (hard-voting). Then, cost-sensitive ensemble model H is defined as:

$$H_B(S) = \operatorname{argmax}_{k \in \{0,1\}} \sum_{i=1}^B h_i^k(S) \quad (6)$$

where the $h_i^k \in \{0, 1\}$ is the output for the class label $k \in \{0, 1\}$. In the soft-voting scenario, the final prediction is obtained as the mean cost-sensitive probability score that is calculated across all cost-sensitive probabilities of the base CSDT models:

$$H_B(S) = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{i=1}^B h_i^k(S) \quad (7)$$

where the $h_i^k \in [0, 1]$ is the cost-sensitive probability score for the class label $k \in \{0, 1\}$.

3.3 | Cost-sensitive tree explainer

The Shapley Additive Explanation Method (SHAP) [20] is an increasingly popular xAI method based on solid mathematical theory. More precisely, the method is based on the Shapley values, a concept from game theory. The SHAP values are defined as the Shapley values of a conditional expectation function of the machine learning model. The Shapley value of each feature is defined as a contribution to the prediction of the sample, weighted and summed over all possible feature combinations. To calculate the weighted average marginal contribution of a feature, all coalitions in which the feature appears should be considered. For that reason, SHAP calculation is a computationally costly task. The total number of possible feature combinations grows exponentially as the number of features increases. To overcome this problem, different approximations, both model-specific and model-agnostic, have been proposed. The Tree SHAP represents a special model-specific SHAP approximation for tree-based models.

The Tree SHAP method enables tractable computation of optimal local explanations with the improvement compared to other approximation methods in the exact computation of the local explanations in polynomial time for tree-based models. The method can be considered as a new tool for a better understanding of global model structure based on many local explanations. Combining many local explanations allows the representation of global structure while retaining local faithfulness to the original model, which produces more detailed and accurate representations of model behavior [21]. This is especially important for deep tree-based models as the depth of the tree can be a limiting factor in comprehending the model's decision for each sample.

For the cost-sensitive tree classifiers besides depth, another limiting factor in comprehending the reasoning behind the decision-making process of the classifier is the fact that the current implementation of the method does not provide a useful graphical representation of the model such as representation for tree-based models implemented in scikit-learn [25]. The cost-sensitive tree models do not have a nice flowchart graph visualization. Moreover, extracting decision rules for individual samples is hard even for shallow cost-sensitive tree models. On the other hand, applying the existing Tree SHAP method was impossible due to the incompatibility of the Tree SHAP and the CSDT algorithm. The CSDT algorithm as explained uses a cost matrix in the tree-building process and terminal nodes. Due to the latter fact, the cost matrix had to be taken into consideration by the Tree SHAP which does not treat a machine learning model as a black box, rather it uses its tree-based structure to compute SHAP values exactly.

In the Tree SHAP algorithm, a conditional expectation function of the model's output is estimated recursively. The conditional expectation function is estimated using tree traversal, an object that contains the information of the tree model such as a vector of node values; the vectors that represent the left and right node indexes for each internal node; the vectors that contain the thresholds and indexes of the feature used for splitting in each internal node. This set of information has to be augmented with a cost matrix, since deciding whether the sample will be classified as positive or negative, depends on the cost matrix.

As the Tree SHAP is supported only for several tree-based models, first it was necessary to define tree traversal functions for cost-sensitive decision tree models. These functions should extract all information needed for the recreation of the tree model, including the information about the cost matrix. Firstly, the CSDT algorithm from `costcla` package [1] is modified in a way that expands attributes of existing tree object, given as dictionary object. This dictionary object is later used as a representation of the trained cost-sensitive tree model. Second, an adaptation of the Tree SHAP algorithm was performed to handle the cost-sensitive tree model. To create the cost-sensitive Tree SHAP (CSTreeSHAP) method as a subclass of TreeSHAP, we have established several recursive functions for extracting required information from the dictionary-represented tree model. In this way, we have enabled the extraction of the explanations of individual samples classified with (deep) cost-sensitive tree-based models using CSTreeSHAP method. For cost-sensitive tree-based ensemble models such as the described CSRF model, explained extraction of information using tree traversal had to be applied for each CSDT classifier.

The SHAP values of all the input features sum up to the difference between the expected model output and the output of the model for the sample being explained. In the classification framework, the expected output is the prior probability of a class and the output of the model is the probability label assigned to a node the sample belongs. This means, that the SHAP values generated by the CSTreeSHAP, sum up to the prior cost-sensitive probability of a class and the cost-sensitive probability output of the cost-sensitive tree-based classifier.

4 | EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The analysis is performed under the Python 3.7 environment, including scikit-learn library [25] version 0.23.1, to be compatible with the `costcla` package [1]. The `costcla` includes different cost-sensitive algorithms that are adapted and used for training machine learning models and certain algorithms from the SHAP package are modified and used for model explanation and interpretation.

In the experimental part of the work, the aim was not to solely test cost-sensitive tree classifier performance and compare it to the performance of standard decision tree (DT) classifier, but to analyze feature importance retrieved from obtained local explanations using the cost-sensitive Tree SHAP (CSTreeSHAP) and Tree SHAP methods for cost-sensitive and cost-insensitive tree-models models, respectively. By providing insight into the decision-making process of different machine learning models it is possible to make evidence-based decisions about models that would be preferable. Further, we analyze whether there is a significant statistical difference between the obtained shap values of the models generated by different learning algorithms. Besides, the analysis is performed for models generated using the same learning algorithm with different tree depth parameter for both single-tree as well as ensemble models. Furthermore, for ensemble models the analysis is extended on investigation of another parameter - the number of base learners in the ensemble model. Results of the analysis are reported in the next section. Since the cost-sensitive tree-based classifiers are seen as a tool well suited for tackling class imbalance problem, the analysis is performed on three imbalanced datasets from financial domain.

4.1 | Datasets

For conducting the experimental part of the work several datasets are used. Two out of the three used datasets are related to credit scoring, a domain with typically imbalanced data distribution, where one, minority class of risky clients has a higher misclassification cost. That is, the minor group of clients is more likely to default on a loan. All datasets are freely available and used in cost-sensitive framework as the cost matrices are example dependent and known for all samples, which are the main reasons for choosing these datasets for the analysis.

CreditScoring1 (CS1) is a dataset from the Kaggle competition "Give Me Some Credit" [8] whose aim was to improve credit scoring by creating state-of-the-art machine learning models which will help banks in determining whether or not a loan should be granted. The dataset is retrieved from `costcla` library [?] as there is available one-hot-encoded version of the data which was used in the work of Correa, B. A. at et. [4] and other studies [3, 19, 22, 23]. The second dataset, CreditScoring2 (CS2) is from Pacific-Asia Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining conference (PAKDD) competition held in 2009. Our work uses a modified version of the dataset with one-hot-encoded features, which is also available in the `costcla` library. The third dataset is from the direct marketing domain (denoted as MKT) and contains information on bank clients that receive cross-sell offers of long-term deposits. It is available at the University of California at Irvine (UCI) Machine Learning Repository and a modified version used in our study, with one-hot-encoded features, is available at the `costcla` repository.

For all credit scoring datasets the cost is zero for correctly predicted outcomes for both classes while for the bank marketing dataset (MKT), the cost for correct classification of minority samples is positive and represents the administrative cost of contacting the client. The cost for a false positive is also equal to the administrative cost as those clients would decline the offer but would be contacted due to the wrong prediction. More information about the cost matrix for the MKT dataset can be found in [6]. For two other credit scoring datasets, the cost matrices are described in [4]. The cost matrices are taken as defined in the mentioned study and varying the parameters in the matrices is not considered in our study, although in future work it might be interesting to see how changing the cost matrix influences behaviour of the cost-sensitive tree-based models and the explanations generated by the CSTreeSHAP.

4.2 | Experimental evaluation

For partitioning a dataset is used 10-fold cross-validation procedure where a model is trained on $K-1$ folds and the left-out fold is used in the testing phase and explaining phase of the model. Several measures are used in the evaluation procedure including precision and recall per class, F_1 score as the weighted harmonic average of macro precision and recall. All these measures are cost-insensitive, hence it is not possible to observe reduction in the misclassification costs by using these measures. For that reason, the performance of the models is compared using the relative cost reduction measure (also called saving score or cost savings in other studies [4, 6, 23]).

In the explaining phase, the SHAP values are calculated for each sample in the test set during the cross-validation procedure. The obtained values can be averaged for each feature on the whole dataset, and represented in the global feature importance plots. This enables us to discover main driving forces of the machine learning model being explained.

As the baseline model, we have used a decision tree and random forest classifiers with incorporated class weights as the framework of our study encompasses tree-based models applied on imbalanced datasets with unequal misclassification costs and using equal weights on such data is not reasonable, since the algorithms will not be able to correctly classify costly samples from minority class. The decision tree (DTw) and random forest (RFw) classifiers with incorporated class weights set to be inversely proportional to the number of samples in each class are denoted as DTw and RFw, respectively.

In our experiments, the only hyperparameters that was varied is the depth of the tree, ranging from 2 to 10, i.e. from shallow to more deeper tree models. All models are trained without pruning procedure, since the satisfying performance results are obtained and there is no indication of the overfitting. In general, for the DTw and RFw the pruning could be applied by the complexity parameter being set to specified value as well as in cost-sensitive tree-based models. The effect of applying pruning on the models could be investigated in future work. For ensemble models, except different tree depth, additionally are tried three different values (10, 30 and 50) for the number of trees in the ensemble.

The reason behind such a setup was the objective to investigate whether two tree-based models trained on the same data using different algorithms with the same tree depth make classifications based on similar indicators and which model would be preferred by domain experts as an end user. Additionally, obtained results allow us to analyze how the depth of the tree influences the model's decision-making process in view of global feature importance. Furthermore, is analysed the stability of the SHAP values for models generated using different algorithm as well as SHAP values for models generated using the same algorithm on different depths. For ensemble models, it is also analysed how number of base learners influences the performance of the model and what is effect of having more base models in ensemble on the performance and decision making process of the ensemble classifier.

5 | RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 | Performance evaluation

Here will be presented results of the performance comparison of the decision tree model with incorporated class weights (DTw) and cost-sensitive tree models (CSDT) with varying the depth of a tree model, evaluated using the relative cost reduction measure (RCR), the most adequate measure for cost-sensitive classifier evaluation as well as mostly used measure for classification problems, the F_1 score. In following figures are also reported results for the ensemble setup, where are compared the RFw models with the same number of base learners (10) at varying depths and the CSRF model with the same parameter setup. The cross-validated results for all datasets, are summarized in following figures (Figures 1- 2). The calculated scores for the

cost-sensitive tree-based models are visualized with green and blue color is used for cost-insensitive models (DTw and RFW), with three different symbol annotations to distinguish results for the three datasets. The diamond, circle and square are used for the CS1, CS2 and MKT datasets, respectively.

(a) Performance evaluation using RCR measure.
FIGURE 1 Single-tree performance evaluation.

(a) Performance evaluation using RCR measure.
 (b) Performance evaluation using F_1 measure.
FIGURE 2 Ensemble tree performance evaluation. Each ensemble model is composed of 10 base tree models.

According to the reported results in Figure 1 several conclusions can be made. Firstly, by observing RCR scores on the left side of the figure, it can be noted that the CSDT model outperforms DTw on the CS2 and MKT datasets regardless of the tree depth. For the CS1 dataset, the conclusion is not that straightforward. At smaller tree depths, both models perform equally well, until tree depth reaches 5, where the DTw model starts to achieve a slightly better reduction of the misclassification cost. However, deeper CSDT models (with tree depth 9 or 10), achieve a RCR score as good as or better than the DTw classifier. Moreover, as the tree depth increases, the CSDT classifier performs consistently well, without increasing the score, while the scores of the DTw increase until the value 6 of the tree depth, and after that, the score starts to decrease. Contrarily, by observing the F_1 scores on the right side of the figure, it can be noted that the DTw classifier outperforms the CSDT across all tree depths

on the CS2 dataset. For the CS1 and MKT datasets, the conclusion is similar, except for the smallest depths, 2 and 3 at which the CSDT model achieves a higher F_1 score.

The results for ensemble tree-based models are reported in Figure 2. As can be noted from the left subfigure, for the MKT dataset, the cost-sensitive random forest model (CSRf) outperforms the random forest with class weights (RFw) across all tree depths in terms of the RCR. Reversely, the RFw model outperforms the CSRf for the MKT dataset in terms of F_1 score across all depths of the trees in the ensemble. On the CS2 dataset, the RFw performs overall better than CSRf in terms of the RCR score, while in terms of the F_1 score the RFw performs better or equally good as the CSRf. Similarly, for CS1 dataset, the RFw performs better at tree depths from 3 up to 10, while for depths 2, 3, and 10, the RCR score achieved by the CSRf exceeds the score achieved by the RFw. In terms of F_1 score on the CS1 dataset, the RFw model is consistently better than CSRf as the tree depth increases.

The question that arises is: *How to choose the best model for a given dataset?* The choice will differ depending on the chosen measure of the evaluation. In a cost-sensitive framework, the most relevant measure would be the RCR score, as the F_1 score is a cost-insensitive measure. From the reported results for single-tree classifiers, it can be observed that regardless of the metric of evaluation, the CSDT method produces classifiers with stable performance across different tree depths. Furthermore, the CSDT outperforms the DTw at small depths for all three datasets. Therefore, the CSDT model might be preferred.

From aspect of explanation, the question is: *Can the explanations for equally good performing models generated using different ML algorithms, help us in the model selection process and how?* Another question, related to the complexity of the single-tree models, is whether shallow tree models should be preferred. The question that follows is how the explanation of models generated using the same algorithm, changes with the changes in the complexity of the model. Similarly, if the complexity of ensemble models is measured with the number of base learners in the ensemble, we should examine what is the effect of this number on the decision-making process of the ensemble classifier? And how stable the SHAP values are for the ensemble models generated with the same algorithm with different number of trees in the model?

To answer all these questions, the introduced CSTreeSHAP is applied on the cost-sensitive tree-based methods (CSDT and CSRf) and Tree SHAP is applied on the cost-insensitive methods (DTw and RFw). The results of the performed analysis are reported in the next subsection.

5.2 | Global feature importance and stability analysis

In general, explanations generated by xAI methods based on SHAP methodology are local, meaning the SHAP values used for explanations are calculated for each sample. Nevertheless, these SHAP values can be used for creating global explanations for the given model. The global feature importance is calculated as mean absolute value for each feature on the whole dataset. Several examples of global feature importance plots are shown on the figures below. For the sake of simplification and a better overview, only the top 10 most important features are visualized.

5.2.1 | Analysis of results for the single-tree models

Recall, a deeper tree models generated using the CSDT perform equally well as smaller trees on the CS1 dataset. For that reason, the plots are shown for tree depths 2, 3, 9 and 10. Firstly, we will give brief analysis of the exposed feature importance plots and thereafter we will try to answer the aforementioned questions.

From the left-hand side plots on Figure 3 can be observed that growing cost-sensitive tree model at larger tree depths is prevented by the internal mechanisms of the CSDT algorithm since the number of important features does not increase as might be expected. That is, the cost-sensitive splitting criterion which does not split the node if there is no reduction of the misclassification cost, leads to termination of splitting process and growing deep tree model. On the other side, the DTw algorithm rather grows deep trees with increasing the tree depth. Additionally, the plots of the CSDT reveal that the CSDT models at different tree depths have consistent ordering of the features, unlike the DTw models, where the same conclusion can not be drawn. For the DTw only the first feature remains the same across all depths. These observations, could be a reason for favoring the CSDT over the DTw models.

For the remaining two datasets (CS2 and MKT), the plots are not shown due to space limitations. However, the conclusions are the same as for the CS1 dataset. The feature ordering for the CSDT models with varying tree depths, does not change unlike the feature ordering for the DTw models.

(a) Global feature importance plot for CSDT at tree depth 2.

(b) Global feature importance plot for DTW at tree depth 2.

(c) Global feature importance plot for CSDT at tree depth 3.

(d) Global feature importance plot for DTW at tree depth 3.

(e) Global feature importance plot for CSDT at tree depth 9.

(f) Global feature importance plot for DTW at tree depth 9.

(g) Global feature importance plot for CSDT at tree depth 10.

(h) Global feature importance plot for DTW at tree depth 10.

FIGURE 3 Single-tree global feature importance for CSDR and DTW at varying tree depths.

FIGURE 4 Global feature importance plots for correctly (left) and wrongly (right) classified samples by the CSDT and DTw at tree depths 2 and 3.

Notice, the presented plots show feature importance as the average value over shap values for all the samples, regardless whether the model classifies the samples correctly or not. Question that arises is: *Are these plots going to change if global feature importance plots are generated separately for correctly and wrongly classified samples?* To be able to compare plots for the trees generated using CSDT and DTw methods, the averaging is done on the overlapping samples that are correctly or wrongly classified by both models. Following figures visualize the most important features for correctly and wrongly classified samples in the CS1 dataset, by both the CSDT and DTw tree models. As before, the plots are reported for depths 2, 3, 9 and 10.

5.2.1.1 | *Results for single-tree cost-sensitive and cost-insensitive models across different tree depths*

On the Figures 4-5 are shown global feature importance plots for the DTw and CSDT classifiers at aforementioned depths for correctly and wrongly classified samples, where the subplots on the left side correspond to the correct samples and right side plots to the misclassified samples.

The same conclusion is drawn by observing plots for correctly and wrongly classified samples from DTw and CSDT classifiers. At all depths, only the most important feature coincides for the DTw and CSDT. Furthermore, both models made correct decision by using similar features. Having the same feature with highest mean absolute SHAP value for both models at different depths for misclassified samples, means the wrong classification of the samples is driven by the same features. The question is: *If two models have the same or similar global feature importance plots, do the SHAP values of the models have the same distribution?* That is, we seek to test whether the explanations generated for different models with similar global importance plots, are statistically significantly different.

Statistical analysis of shap values per feature is performed using Mann-Whitney test [14], a non-parametric significance test. The question of the test is whether the difference between the central tendency (mean) of the SHAP values, is statistically significant. The null hypothesis of the test is the assumption that both samples (SHAP values for the same feature of different

FIGURE 5 Global feature importance plots for correctly (left) and wrongly (right) classified samples by the CSDT and DTw at tree depths 9 and 10.

models) were drawn from a population with the same distribution. The p-value is a probability of observing the two shap values vectors given the base assumption (null hypothesis) that the samples were drawn from a population with the same distribution. The p-value can be interpreted in the context of a chosen significance level alpha. In experiments is used 0.05 as the value for alpha. If the p-value is below the significance level, then the test says there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis and that the samples were likely drawn from populations with differing distributions.

The test is performed for the features that appear to be most important for decision-making process of the DTw and CSDT, separately for correct and misclassified samples. The results of the performed testing are briefly discussed and not reported due to space limitations.

Results for CS1 dataset reveal that the null hypothesis is rejected for all features regardless if the SHAP values are considered for correctly or wrongly classified samples. This means that the explanations for the two models, the DTw and CSDT, are statistically significantly different, although based on the plots it might seem that the models provide the same explanations.

For the other two datasets, the same analysis is performed. For the CS2 dataset, the CSDT model regardless of tree depth, builds the same model with only one feature, the *Personal net Income*. Testing the hypothesis for the feature reveals that there is a significant difference between SHAP values for the CSDT and DTw classifiers at all tree depths. For DTw models, global feature importance plots show that the feature appears in the lower positions of the importance plot depending on the tree depth for both correctly and wrongly classified samples.

By comparing plots for correctly classified samples in the MKT dataset, it can be concluded that the driving forces of DTw and CSDT for making correct decisions on the same samples, differ. It can also be observed that CSDT makes correct as well as wrong decisions based on the same two features at varying tree depths, while DTw for both decisions considers an increasing number of features as the tree depth increases with the same most important feature for both correct and wrong classifications.

5.2.1.2 | Results for single-tree cost-sensitive/cost-insensitive models at different tree depths

Influence of the tree depth on the single-tree model stability is also analysed. Here the hypothesis is tested for SHAP values of the single-tree model generated using the same machine learning algorithm at sequential tree depths.

The results for CS1 dataset and the CSDT models show that for the smaller depths the hypothesis is rejected for both correct and misclassified samples. However, for correct samples, starting from the depth 6 (and for misclassified samples, starting from the depth 7), there is enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis, meaning there is no significant difference between SHAP values of the CSDT model for top-4 features (*UnsecuredLines*, *Times90DaysLate*, *DaysPastDue30-59*, *DaysPastDue60-89*) at depths 6 (CSDT-6) and CSDT at depth 7 (CSDT-7), as well as between CSDT-7 and CSDT-8, CSDT-8 and CSDT-9, and between CSDT-9 and CSDT-10. For the DTw models on the CS1 dataset, the results are the same for correct and misclassified samples, with several exceptions in terms of depth scenarios. Firstly, for the feature *DaysPastDue60-89*, the hypothesis is rejected in all compared depth scenarios. Secondly, for other three features listed above, the hypothesis is rejected only for DTw at depths 2 and 3. For all other scenarios, the results of the testing indicate that there is no difference between SHAP values of the three features for DTw models at different tree depths.

For CS2 dataset and CSDT models, as expected, the hypothesis tested for the most important feature is accepted for both correct and misclassified samples in all depth scenarios. For the DTw models on the CS2 dataset, although the number of features on global importance plots increases as the tree depth increases, the top-rated feature (*Age*) remains in the top position across all tree depths. Interestingly, the hypothesis for the feature is not rejected for all tree depth scenarios for both, the correct and misclassified samples.

For the CSDT models trained on the MKT dataset, the results of the testing indicate that the test is rejected for the classifiers with smaller depths. That is, there is statistically significant difference between the SHAP values of the top rated features for the CSDT models at depth 2 (CSDT-2) and CSDT model with depth 3 (CSDT-3). The same results of the testing are obtained for the CSDT-3 and CSDT-4. For all other depths scenarios the hypothesis is accepted. For the DTw models, the hypothesis is not rejected for three features, one of them being the top-rated regardless of the tree depth, in all depth scenarios for both, the correct and misclassified samples.

Based on the analysis on single-tree models, we can conclude that there are differences between the explanations of the CSDT and DTw models trained with the same tree depth, although the global feature importance plots show the models use similar indicators in the decision-making process. The explanations for the CSDT models at different depths differ for smaller trees and for more larger trees the explanations generated are not statistically significantly different. For that reason and the fact that the CSDT outperforms the DTw at the smaller depths in terms of RCR, the best model of choice would be the CSDT model with a small tree depth. The depth of the tree could be chosen based on the results of the testing the hypothesis. We would choose the model with tree depth d if the result of the testing is to accept the hypothesis for the models with the tree depth higher than d .

5.2.2 | Analysis of results for the ensemble models

Here will be presented results of the analysis for the cost-sensitive and cost-insensitive random forest models, annotated as the CSRF and RFw, respectively. To keep consistency with the results reported for single-tree models, the feature importance plots are shown only for CS1 dataset. Furthermore, the plots are shown for the same tree depths as for the single-tree models. Recall, the CSRF outperforms the RFw when tree depth of the base learners is small 2 or 3, with the exception on the largest depth analysed, where the CSRF also performs better than the RFw in terms of the RCR score. Figure 6 shows global feature importance plots for ensemble tree models at tree depths 2, 3, 9 and 10.

Notably, for the CSRF models even at the small tree depths 2 and 3, there is much larger number of features compared to single-tree cost-sensitive models at the same tree depths. However, the ordering of the features is preserved at smaller depths. Interestingly, starting from the tree depth 4, the second and third feature change positions depending on the tree depth. This change can be observed at the global feature importance plot for tree depths 9 and 10. Regarding the cost-insensitive ensemble models, the conclusion is the same as for single cost-insensitive tree models. At varying tree depths, the RFw algorithm grows tree models with more variation in ordering of the important features compared to the cost-sensitive random forest models, excluding the first two features that remain on the same positions.

Similarly as for CS1 dataset, for the CS2 and MKT datasets, there is much more features listed on global feature importance plots. Recall for the single CSDT models trained on the CS2 dataset, there is only one important feature across all tree depths. More features for cost-sensitive ensemble models trained on the same data can be explained by the fact that each base learner (CSDT) in the CSRF is trained on a randomly chosen subset of features. For that reason, the only appearing feature in the plots

(a) Global feature importance plot for CSRF at tree depth 2.

(b) Global feature importance plot for RFw at tree depth 2.

(c) Global feature importance plot for CSRF at tree depth 3.

(d) Global feature importance plot for RFw at tree depth 3.

(e) Global feature importance plot for CSRF at tree depth 9.

(f) Global feature importance plot for RFw at tree depth 9.

(g) Global feature importance plot for CSRF at tree depth 10.

(h) Global feature importance plot for RFw at tree depth 10.

FIGURE 6 Ensemble tree global feature importance at varying tree depths.

for CSDT models trained on the CS2, might be excluded from the subset, leading the algorithm to choose some other feature at the first split in the building a tree in an ensemble. Regardless, the top-rated feature for CSRF models is the same as for single CSDT models at varying depths. Apart from the first two features, the ordering of other features is changing across the models at different depths. This top-rated feature has less importance on the plots for the cost-insensitive models across all tree depths. Analysis of the plots for the MKT dataset leads to the same conclusions drawn for the CS2 dataset.

In the ensemble setup, the Mann-Whitney test was conducted for three different purposes. Firstly, we test whether there is a difference between the mean of the SHAP values for the cost-sensitive and cost-insensitive ensemble models with the same number of base learners across different tree depths. Secondly, we test whether there is a difference between the mean of the SHAP values for the models generated using the same ensemble learning algorithm with the same number of estimators across different depths. Lastly, we test whether there is a difference between the mean of the shap values for the models generated using the same ensemble learning algorithm with a different number of estimators at the same tree depths.

In the same way, as for single-tree models, the test is performed separately for correctly and misclassified samples by the models whose SHAP values are being compared.

5.2.2.1 | Results for the cost-sensitive and cost-insensitive ensemble models with the same number of the base learners across different tree depths

Results for the CSRF and RfW composed from 10 base tree models trained on the CS1 dataset reveal that for correctly classified samples, the hypothesis is rejected for all features across all tree depths, except for depth 6 where the test failed to reject the hypothesis for the feature *Times90DaysLate* which is one of the top-3 rated features in both models. For wrongly classified samples, there is no significant difference between SHAP values of some features at some depths, without some clear pattern.

According to the results for the analysed ensemble models on the CS2 dataset, for the correct samples the hypothesis is not rejected for some features at some depths, while for the wrongly classified samples, the hypothesis is not rejected mostly for the depths smaller than 5, still without some clear consistency in rejection.

Similarly for the MKT dataset, results show that the hypothesis is not rejected only for some features at some tree depths, without any interesting notable pattern.

5.2.2.2 | Results for the cost-sensitive/cost-insensitive ensemble models with the same number of the base learners at different tree depths

Secondly, we test whether there is a difference between the mean of the SHAP values for the models generated using the same ensemble learning algorithm with the same number of estimators at different tree depths. The results for the CSRF models trained on the CS1 dataset, with the ten CSDT trees, at different tree depths, indicate that for correctly classified samples for models trained on depths 3 and 4 (CSRF-3 and CSRF-4), the hypothesis is not rejected for the top-rated feature *UnsecuredLines*, while for misclassified samples for the same models the hypothesis is rejected. Interestingly, for misclassified samples, the hypothesis is not rejected after depth 7. That is, there is no statistically significant difference between SHAP values for the top-rated feature between CSRF-7 and CSRF-8, CSRF-8 and CSRF-9, and CSRF-9 and CSRF-10. For other features, there is no clear pattern (in terms of specific tree depth or specific feature) when the hypothesis is not rejected. For the cost-insensitive ensemble classifiers with ten estimators, the hypothesis is not rejected for the top-rated feature for CSRF-8 and CSRF-9 for correctly classified samples, and for CSRF-7 and CSRF-8 for wrongly classified samples. For other features, the hypothesis is rejected for some depths but without some clear pattern for correctly nor misclassified samples.

For the CS2 dataset, the test performed on the CSRF ensemble models composed of the ten CSDT classifiers at different depths is not rejected for top-rated feature for correctly classified samples up to depth 7 with exception for the depths 3 and 4, where the hypothesis is rejected. For misclassified samples, the hypotheses tested for SHAP values of the top-rated feature are rejected for CSRF models at sequential depth. For RfW ensemble models with ten estimators at different depths, the hypothesis is rejected in several cases, without a notable pattern.

For the MKT dataset in the same experimental setup with base ten estimators, the hypothesis is not rejected for some features for some pairs of CSRF models being tested. There is no clear overlap between the rejection of the hypotheses for the correctly and wrongly classified samples. For example, the hypothesis might be rejected for correctly classified samples and CSRF models at some depths for observed features, while not being rejected for misclassified samples and the same models at the same depths. For the RfW ensemble classifiers with ten base trees, the hypothesis is rejected in many more cases for misclassified samples, still, it is not possible to extract some general conclusion.

In the experimental setup with the number of base estimators changed and set to 30 or 50, a similar conclusion for all three datasets can be made for both cost-sensitive and cost-insensitive ensemble models trained. In either scenario, no general

conclusion can be made about cases in which the SHAP values of the models being tested are not statistically significantly different. Although the ensemble models are generated using the same learning algorithm, the models obtained give different explanations even if the global feature importance plots might suggest differently.

5.2.2.3 | *Results for the cost-sensitive/cost-insensitive ensemble models across different numbers of the base learners at the same tree depths*

For this experimental setup, the aim was to analyze the influence of different number of estimators in an ensemble model, both cost-sensitive and cost-insensitive. To provide more deeper analysis, the setup is tested for different tree depths. The testing is conducted for SHAP values obtained on ensemble models with 10 estimators versus SHAP values obtained on ensemble models with 30 estimators. The same setup is used for testing models with 30 and 50 estimators.

For the CS1 dataset and CSRF models with 10 and CSRF models with 30 estimators, the hypotheses tested for SHAP values of the models across different depths are rejected for almost all features regardless if we test SHAP values of the correctly or misclassified samples. There are several negligible exceptions where the test fails to reject hypothesis for some features of the misclassified samples. The same is observed on the results for the CSRF models with 30 and 50 estimators. For cost-insensitive models (RFw) in both comparison setups (10 vs 30 estimators, and 30 vs 50 estimators), it is interesting that the hypothesis is rejected in all cases for correctly classified samples, while for the misclassified samples there are several cases where the hypothesis is not rejected.

According to the results for the CS2 dataset, and CSRF with 10 and 30 estimators, the hypothesis is rejected in large number of cases with a slightly more cases in which the test fails to reject it, compared to the results on the CS1 dataset. The same conclusion is made for testing hypothesis for CSRF with 30 and CSRF with 50 estimators. Furthermore, the same is observed for RFw models.

Lastly, for the MKT dataset, the same conclusion can be drawn as for the previously analysed datasets, both cost-sensitive as well for cost-insensitive ensemble models. There are cases when the test fails to reject the hypothesis, yet any general pattern cannot be extracted. Notably, the rejection happens more for misclassified samples, although not for any specific feature across all tree depths nor for all features at the specific tree depths.

6 | CONCLUDING REMARKS

The purpose of this article is to provide an extension of our previous work on the Cost-sensitive TreeSHAP (CSTreeSHAP) method to address cost-sensitive ensemble models, specifically focusing on tree-based models. This research builds upon that foundation by extending the methodology to cost-sensitive ensemble models, addressing a broader scope of applications. The CSTreeSHAP method can be seen as an xAI tool for better understanding the driving forces behind the decision-making process of cost-sensitive classifiers, with a focus on tree-based models. Moreover, the CSTreeSHAP facilitates the interpretation of ensemble models where base models are generated using the cost-sensitive decision tree (CSDT) learning algorithm.

Theoretical contribution is provided through the adaptation of the Tree SHAP algorithm to handle the cost-sensitive tree-based models, considering the cost matrix incorporated in the tree-building process. Furthermore, the labeling scheme in the CSDT algorithm is changed from hard-labeling to soft-labeling. The soft-labeling is introduced with cost-sensitive probabilities, thereby keeping the labeling of the nodes cost-sensitive. In this way, the CSTreeSHAP generates SHAP values that sum up to the cost-sensitive probability of a class and the cost-sensitive probability output of the cost-sensitive tree classifier being explained.

The usefulness of the CSTreeSHAP method is demonstrated through experimental evaluation. The empirical contribution is demonstrated through the application of the CSTreeSHAP method on cost-sensitive tree-based models trained on various datasets. The analysis is performed by varying tree depths and number of trees for ensemble models, showcasing the ability of the CSTreeSHAP to provide both local and global explanations for cost-sensitive tree models. Having the ability to compare explanations for cost-insensitive and cost-sensitive tree models enables well-grounded model selection. For single-tree cost-sensitive models, results indicate that explanations provided by the CSTreeSHAP for the deep CSDT models are not statistically significantly different. For that reason and due to the over-performance of the CSDT classifier at the small tree depths over the cost-insensitive single-tree model at the same tree depths, the small CSDT models might be preferable. According to the results for the cost-sensitive tree-based ensemble models, it is not possible to extract some general conclusion since the testing hypotheses results in rejection without a notable pattern.

Except for being well-suited for cost-sensitive problems, the potential of the CStreeSHAP and cost-sensitive tree-classifier can be seen in providing explanations for a large number of imbalanced data on which the cost-sensitive tree-building methodology could be applied.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

All authors contributed to the study's conception and design. Methodology: MK and MS and SB; Experimental analysis: MK. Drafting of the article: MK and SH; Critical revision of the article: all authors. All authors have read and approved the manuscript for submission.

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The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no potential conflict of interests.

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